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MLKL and TBK1 activation in the blood in Crohn's Disease.

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The TANK-binding kinase 1 (TBK1) resides downstream of the RIP kinases (RIPK1-4) and MLKL in a collection of pathways that regulate the balance between death and effector function. We describe here activation of MLKL and TBK1 in the blood of humans with inflammatory bowel disease Crohn's Disease. The described enrichment reflects either a specific pathway activation associated with disease susceptibility (directly or indirectly) associated with NOD2 (which resides upstream of RIPK2), or a general association between cell death pathways and disease in humans with chronic disease.